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Social Policy, Social Problem and Social Work in Nigeria: A Critical Approach

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on social policy, social problems, and social work in Nigeria: A critical approach. The study employed systems theory, as Nigeria is seen as unit with its component parts. This stated that social problems such unemployment, poverty, health, poor educational standard, and insecurity are systemic challenges facing Nigeria. Despite this, it has not been addressed appropriately using short term policy approach and in appropriate intervention strategy. The qualitative data was employed using published literatures from textbooks, journals, and articles, in order to address the prevailing social problems facing Nigeria. Social Workers are supposed to play an interventionist role in tackling social problems in Nigeria, but poor recognition, underfunding and corrupt practices among government officials encountered has undermined their impact remarkably. The intervention made by government has not yielded the required aim as well as social work intervention, since social workers solely relies on relationship with community, advocacy role, and social development initiatives. The study concluded that there is need to improve social work practice and adopt the right social policies to address the lingering social problem to improve the wellbeing of citizens of the country. It was recommended that government needs to plan policy to control the rising insecurity issues, educational challenges, health issues and economic issues in Nigeria.

Keywords: Social Policy, Social Problem, Social Work

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, social policy, social problems, and social work are concepts that have not been given thorough attention over the years. As scholars has begin to see the reasons why these concepts would be integrated. Social policy refers to the tactics and measures taken by the state to address citizens' social needs. Within this framework, social work as a professional discipline work to advance human well-being, social justice, and social functioning. Researchers stress that comprehending these ideas collectively is crucial for evaluating welfare systems, particularly in developing nations, like Nigeria (Barr, 2025).

However, the state's attempt to tackle social policies on protection, housing, health care, and education is known as social policy. Over the years, Nigeria has implemented a number of social policies to

improve welfare and lessen vulnerability, such as the National Social Protection Policy and Social Investment Policies. In the society, inadequate funding, corruption, inconsistent policy, and poor implementation have all compromised the efficiency of existing government policies. Today, a lot of Nigerian social policies prioritize short-term welfare assistance, over addressing the causes of social problems, which is not sustainable, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria (Ogunnubi, 2025). There are many policies which past governments have initiated that have not yielded the desired outcomes, thereby rendering the populace in impoverished.

In Nigeria, social work is a vital mediator between social policy and social issues to meet the various needs of individuals at different levels in the society. For instance, social work address the challenges facing the communities using casework, community development, advocacy, and policy practice. However, the profession is confronted with obstacles like restricted institutional support, weak legal support, and little or no recognition. Nigeria as a country has not recognized the relevance of social work profession, unlike in the developed nations where they give this profession more relevance. Therefore, in order to appreciate the effort of the social workers, there is need for strengthening their efforts through policies, participatory practice and interventionist role at all levels to meet the social needs of the people, development and social justice initiatives (Cummins et al., 2023).

Theoretical Review

Ludwig von Bertalanffy, an Austrian biologist was the first to develop the General Systems Theory (GST) in 1940s and published significant works between 1945 and 1968. He was credited for creating the systems theory of social work (Bertalanffy, 1951). Systems theory in social work highlights that people must be viewed as components of interconnected systems, including the family, community, institutions, economy, and larger society, rather than as isolated entities. As social work moved from strictly individual-focused interventions to more holistic and environmental approaches, this theoretical viewpoint gained momentum (Payne, 2014).

From the system theory point of view, the society is seen as collection of interconnected and interdependent subsystems, and any change in one will unavoidably have an impact on the others. Naturally, in social work practice, it is assumed that social issues like poverty, unemployment, crime, domestic abuse, child neglect and other forms of social problems are not just personal shortcomings, but rather the result of intricate relationships between social, political, economic, cultural, and personal systems. As Zastrow emphasized that social work's professional mandate is aimed towards enhancing social functioning of the people's as well as their wellbeing in the environments (Zastrow, 2017).

Nigeria is seen as a country with a unit, with its component parts, with myriad problems surrounding the nation. In relation to social policy, systems theory is particularly useful because it highlights the interconnectedness of policies and social outcomes. In Nigeria, social policies in areas of education, health, housing, employment, and social welfare operate as subsystems within the broader national system. Typically when the government makes useful policies that are favourable in one areas, may fail in other areas, but subjects to medication as time goes by. Gray (2023) was also in support of this assumption by saying that the systems theory therefore provides a framework for understanding why fragmented or poorly coordinated social policies in Nigeria often fail to achieve their intended goals. It encourages policymakers and social workers to adopt integrated and comprehensive policy approaches, rather than isolated interventions.

Systems theory typically provides a potent explanatory lens for social issues in Nigeria. Many of Nigeria's enduring societal issues, including poverty, substance misuse, street begging, family breakup, young unemployment, and insecurity, are systemic rather than personal. For instance, it is impossible to fully understand urban crime in large cities or teenage restlessness in the Niger Delta without looking at the interplay between political marginalization, inadequate institutions, poor governance (Iwarimie-Jaja & Raimi, 2018), cultural issues, and economic disparity. By identifying how these various systems interact to create and maintain social issues. It was argued that the system theory

assists social workers in avoiding oversimplified explanations that place the responsibility solely on individuals or families (Kurevakwesu, 2024).

Literature Review

Social Policy

The term "social policy" describes the methodical decisions and activities made by governments and pertinent organizations to advance social welfare and meet societal demands including social protection, employment, housing, health care, and education. It offers a framework for enhancing living circumstances, lowering vulnerability, and guaranteeing citizens' social fairness. Social policy is seen by modern academics as a crucial tool for national development, especially in nations where poverty and inequality are pervasive (Cummins et al., 2023). Social policy, for instance, is influenced by social, political, and economic factors and represents the objectives and values of individuals in positions of authority. It establishes the distribution of resources, the recipients of welfare programs, and the management of social risks. Social policy frequently addresses systemic issues including social exclusion, poor institutions, and unemployment in emerging nations. According to recent evaluations, effective social policy must incorporate participation, empowerment, and rights-based strategies in addition to welfare provision (Gray & Amadasun, 2023; Elebshehe, 2024).

In Nigeria, social policy is essential for tackling enduring societal issues like unemployment, poverty, inequality, poor health outcomes, and insecurity. To reduce social risks and safeguard vulnerable groups, the government has implemented programs including the National Social Protection Policy, National Social Investment Programs, Universal Basic Education, Health Insurance, policies, etc. However, empirical research indicates that low finance, poor coordination, corruption, and weak implementation procedures have hampered the impact of these policies (Federal Government of Nigeria Ogunnubi, 2025).

In a 2024 Social Protection Program was developed by the government to address social issues to boost the economy. There has been considerable success in reducing poverty and improving access to basic services, and recent assessments of Nigeria's social safety programs show that results are still inconsistent among socioeconomic classes and geographical areas. Women, children, people with disabilities, and rural populations are still severely excluded. Nigeria's social policy framework, according to academics, frequently lacks sustainability and policy continuity, resulting in short-term interventions rather than long-term social improvement.

From the standpoint of social work, social policy offers the institutional framework in which professional activity takes place. In addition to providing services, social workers participate in social policy as advocates and analysts. According to recent research, Nigerian social workers are increasingly involved in community development, human rights-based interventions, and policy advocacy with the goal of influencing social policy outcomes (Enekoga & Owoyemi, 2025).

Critics contend that system stability is frequently given precedence above social fairness in Nigerian social policy. Without addressing the fundamental structural causes of social problems like inequality, political marginalization, and bad governance, policies may only address their symptoms. In order to guarantee that social policies actually advance social development and human dignity, a postcolonial and critical approach to social policy necessitates inclusive policy design, community involvement, and accountability. Accordingly, social policy is still an essential instrument for resolving social issues and advancing welfare in Nigeria. Recent assessments, however, highlight the necessity of rights-based, integrated, and participatory social policies backed by robust institutions and expert social work practice. For Nigerians to achieve sustainable growth and a higher standard of living, the relationship between social work and social policy must be strengthened (Kurevakwesu, 2024).

Social Problem

There are several ways to define social problems, but differs from one scholar to another. According to Spicker (2014), a social problem is any circumstance or scenario that adversely impacts a large number of people, jeopardizes societal ideals, and necessitates group action to be resolved. When

public expectations and real social reality diverge, misery, inequality, or dysfunction result. Social problem is a situation where it becomes a social problem not only because it occurs but also because it is socially acknowledged as detrimental and necessitates response through social action, social policy, or professional practice like social work.

From the societal standpoints, social issues are more than just personal shortcomings; they are systemic and institutional. For instance, problems like poverty, unemployment, crime, broken families, bad health, and inequality frequently emerge from institutional flaws, political systems, cultural norms, and economic structures. According to a recent assessment, analyzing how social systems interact and how opportunities, power, and resources are dispersed unevenly across society is necessary to comprehend social problems (Gray & Amadasun, 2023).

In line with this, Ogunbiyi (2025) reiterated that social problems are pervasive and intricately linked in Nigeria. Despite the nation's wealth of natural and human resources, poverty is one of the most enduring societal issues, affecting a sizable section of the populace. Unemployment, underemployment, low earnings, inflation, and inadequate social safety systems are all associated with poverty in Nigeria. Research demonstrates that various social issues such as poor health, low educational attainment, child labor, and social isolation are also causes and effects of poverty.

Social Work in Nigeria

In the past, welfare services offered by missionaries, nonprofits, and colonial officials played a major role in the development of social work practice in Nigeria during the colonial era. These early welfare initiatives concentrated on providing basic community support, child welfare, and relief services. After independence in 1960, the Nigerian government expanded social welfare services, leading to the formalization of social work education and practice in universities and training institutions. Despite this progress, the profession has continued to struggle for full recognition and professional regulation compared to other helping professions (Ekpenyong & Raimi, 2008; Okoye & Obikeze, 2016).

In Nigeria, social work is a professional and academic field that aims to improve social functioning, advance social justice, and enhance the welfare of individuals, families, communities, and groups. It focuses on using professional intervention, social policy advocacy, community development, and vulnerable population empowerment to address social issues. In Nigeria, social work as a profession is based on both contemporary professional practices influenced by Western social work traditions and local assisting methods (Gray & Amadasun, 2023).

Additionally, Social Work, is a wide range of social concerns which tackles issues related to poverty, unemployment, child abuse, domestic violence, substance misuse, disability, aging, health issues, and insecurity. Social workers engage in community development initiatives, they play advocacy role, intermediary role between the community and government when they are facing with one problem to another. They offer guidance and counseling role to victims when they are faced with one form of challenges to another. This can be marital issue, health issue, psychological issue, etc.

They also offer community mobilization as a way to facilitate community development at all levels. For example through community mobilization the youths can be empowered through skills acquisition, advocacy, program planning, and policy implementation. Nigerian social workers are essential in helping vulnerable populations like women, children, internally displaced people (IDPs), and people with disabilities (Enekoga & Owoyemi, 2025).

In Nigeria, social development and social policy are intimately related to social work. Social workers interact with national programs including the National Social Protection Policy, laws pertaining to child rights, health and education policies, and initiatives aimed at reducing poverty. Social workers endeavor to ensure that social programs are inclusive, equitable, and sensitive to the needs of vulnerable people by influencing policy formulation and implementation through lobbying and policy practice. Researchers contend that in order for social work practice in Nigeria to be effective, macro-level interventions that address social injustice and structural inequality must be included in addition to remedial services (Barr, 2025).

From the above discussion, the depiction below indicates the link between social problem, social policy and social work in Nigeria

Fig. 1: Depiction showing the link between social policy, social problem and social work in Nigeria.

The depiction describes various social policy initiated by government. It includes educational policies, employment policies, inflation policies and security policies. These policies help in addressing the social problem of poverty, unemployment, poor health condition, low educational standard, inflation and insecurity in Nigeria. In a collaborative efforts, the social workers intervenes through casework, counseling, community mobilization, advocacy, program planning and policy implementation to improve the well-being of citizens in the country.

Challenges Facing Social Work in Nigeria

There are many challenges affecting social work, but this few are identified in this study.

Poor Government Commitment to Social Work: Many people think social work doesn't even exist, let alone receive government backing and commitment. Social work is a profession that plays a significant role in every country. They provide guidance and counseling services, professional advice to patients facing various health challenges, and give expert advice to families facing marital crises. However, the advancement of social work in Nigeria has been hampered by the government's continued lack of commitment. For this reason, it has been noted that the lack of acknowledgment for social work is a hindrance to the profession's advancement (Agwu&Okoye, 2021).

Poor Funding: Social work is still inadequate in many Nigerian institutions, since the sector has not received enough funding. It is very costly to incorporate social work into the curricula of universities and other postsecondary institutions, and the government, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders have not provided the necessary funding. For this reason, all of these parties must cooperate to advance social work at universities and throughout the country (Alamu, 2022).

Corrupt Practices of Government Officials: Today, due to the corrupt actions practiced by some public servants it has undermined the professions of social work in Nigeria. Sometime, most of the funds invested across tertiary institutions to advance social work as a profession are frequently diverted by so-called government officials, who frequently use these resources for their own selfish and personal aggrandizements. As a result, the government's planned policies are not carried out. It has been noted that social workers frequently labor in underfunded organizations and face structural problems such as political meddling, corruption, and inconsistent policy. These limitations increase the persistence of social issues and reduce the efficacy of social work interventions (Gray & Amadasun, 2024).

Poor Training and Development: Many social workers in society lack the necessary training and growth to function as social workers. Therefore, enhancing the skills of social workers through training and development may be the best option to function effectively, this can go a long way to improve social work in Nigeria (Omorogiuwa, 2023).

Ways of Addressing Social Work Issues in Nigeria

There are many ways of addressing social work issues in Nigeria. This study has limited it to four ways, as it follows;

Effective Regulatory Framework: There is need for effective regulatory framework, this can go a long way in creating a guiding principle for operational standard of social work profession in Nigeria. It has been noticed that there have been weak enforcement of regulatory body which has poorly affected professional standards, ethical practice, and public trust in social work. For example, creating and empowering a National Council for Social Work in Nigeria would help regulate training institutions, license practitioners, and enforce professional ethics in the Social Work Profession. Therefore, a strong regulation would help in preventing unqualified individuals from practicing social work and enhance professional recognition within the policy environment (Omorogiuwa, 2023). For example, the reason why social work as a professional has not yielded the best outcome is because there are no appropriate regulatory framework in the practice of social work. If for example, government, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders work collaboratively in setting regulatory framework social work would be recognized, not only in Nigeria but other part of the world. Through the regulatory framework, the social work can make advancement in research and development to gain a national and international recognition.

Government Funding: One vital way of improving social work in Nigeria is government funding. Fund is very important in making advancement, research and development in the area of social work and welfare services. For instance, increased government funding and institutional support for social welfare services can help in the transformation of social work. In the society, inadequate fund could limit service delivery, increases caseloads, and weakens interventions for vulnerable groups such as children, older persons, and victims of violence. Also, when the Federal Government of Nigeria improved budgetary allocation to social development ministries and social welfare agencies, would enhance program effectiveness, staff welfare, and infrastructural capacity. When government injects funds into the profession of social work it can enable the social workers to participate meaningfully in national development and poverty reduction efforts (Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN, 2021).

Improving Educational Standard: One way of addressing social work issue in Nigeria is by improving the educational standard. This can come by training and development of workers through higher institutions, seminars, symposium, etc. and by so doing it will promote social work as a vital field of academic profession in Nigeria. Educational standard in social work can be enhanced in increasing skills of social work professionals, today many social workers lack access to updated skills in areas such as community development, policy advocacy, trauma care, guidance and counseling, etc. (Omorogiuwa, 2023). For instance, standardizing social work curricula across universities and strengthening educational field would improve competence and professionalism. Also, educational

standard can be improved when there is continuous training to ensure that practitioners responds effectively to emerging social problems related to insecurity, migration, and family disintegration.

Public Awareness and Orientation:Public awareness and orientation is about sensitizing members of the public about social work as a field of study and practice. Social work practice can be brought into limelight when there is increase public awareness and orientation programme across local government, state, and nation at large. Social work in Nigeria is often poorly understood and undervalued, reducing its influence on policymaking and community engagement. Public enlightenment campaigns and stronger collaboration between social workers, policymakers, and civil society organizations would improve visibility and impact. Integrating social workers into policy formulation and implementation processes ensures that social policies are people-centered and responsive to real community needs (World Bank, 2022). For a sensitization programme to be achieved, social work can be aired on radio, television, and social networks to create more orientation about the field of study as globally recognized and practiced all around the world.

Method of Data Collection

The qualitative data was used in this study to determine social problem and social work in Nigeria: A critical Approach. The data will be determine descriptively, using already published journals, articles, and textbooks.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Impact of Social Policy on Social Problems and Outcomes

Social Policy Focus	Social Problems	Government Interventions	Outcomes	Societal Impact
Social Control & Security Policies	Insecurity Issues like banditry in Northern part of Nigeria , armed robbery and kidnapping in southern part of Nigeria, etc	Poverty reduction strategies, police force intervention, community policing, and youth skills acquisition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce poverty level and improve the source of livelihood throughout the country. Address the issues of insecurity such as armed robbery, kidnapping, and banditry. 	Improve the level of security to boost the economy at all levels.
Labour and Employment Policy	High level of unemployment	Provision of job opportunities by government and other viable investors locally and foreign investors, youth empowerment programmes, etc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve employment opportunities for youths to attract foreign investors. Establish empowerment schemes to liberate the people from hardship. 	Enhance members of the public income, create economic stability, and increase good source of livelihood.
Education Policies on basic education, teacher training and funding	Poor educational standard	Mobilization of fund into the educational sectors (Tertiary, Secondary and Universal Basic Education) in Nigeria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate educational policies through government interventions to provide infrastructures for classrooms , laboratories and other teaching aids 	Increases the level human capital development and sustainability
Economic Policy on Infrastructural Development	Experience of Underdevelopment in the Niger Delta Region	Investment in infrastructure, rural development, and industrialization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved economic growth and regional development 	Reduction in poverty and balanced national development

Source: Online, 2026.

The table above indicated the influence of social policy on social problems. Through this government have been able to intervene by bringing strategies on poverty reduction, youth skills acquisition, etc t reduce poverty level and insecurity challenges in Nigeria to improve the level of security.

Labour and employment policy were initiated to achieve high level of employment. This can be achieved with the collaboration of government with local and foreign investors to improve employment opportunities in Nigeria. This is geared towards enhancing members of the public incomes, create economic stability and increase source of livelihood for the citizens.

The policies in primary and universal health are established to tackle persistent health issues. To address this government can intervene by expansion of primary healthcare and universal health centres across the country. They also plan policies to create more health centres throughout the country and to improve the living standard of the people, there by bringing social change and transformation into the health sectors in Nigeria.

In the part of educational policy on basic education, teacher training and funding. They experience poor educational standard. This can be mitigated by mobilization of fund into the educational sectors (Tertiary, Secondary and Universal Basic Education) in Nigeria. Its outcome is to facilitate educational policies through government interventions to provide infrastructures for classrooms , laboratories and other teaching aids. The impact is all about increasing the level human capital development and sustainability.

Consequently, economic policy on infrastructure in the problem of underdevelopment in the Niger Delta Region. Government intervention is about providing investments on infrastructure, rural development and industrialization for improved economic growth and reduction in poverty, and national development.

CONCLUSION

In any nation, social problems cannot be eroded; there are problems like unemployment, educational problems, economic problems, youth restiveness, like armed robbery, kidnapping, banditry, etc. Social Policies are meant to guide members of the public to ensure their rights have not been violated. The federal government intervenes more often by bringing poverty reduction strategies, youth acquisition and other measures to reduce poverty level and insecurity challenges in Nigeria to improve the level of security.

In the society, to enhance the source of livelihood, labour and employment policy can be initiated to achieve high level of employment. Therefore, in order to achieve this, there is need for collaboration of government with local and foreign investors to improve employment opportunities in Nigeria. There have been uprising social problems in primary and universal health government interventions often helps in making planned policies to bring about the needed social change and transformation in the country.

Education remains one of the greatest instruments for societal development, yet, there are challenges surrounding members of the public. Therefore, there is need for government to make the appropriate social policy for mobilization of fund into the educational sector to mitigate social problems facing citizens of the country.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations made, among others, include:

- i) Government needs to plan policy to control the rising insecurity issues, educational, health issues and economic issues in Nigeria. This can go a long way in mitigating the exiting problem.
- ii) Social Workers need to be strengthened more by adding it as part of the tertiary school curriculum across University in Nigeria.
- iii) There is need for government funding to improve the social work discipline and this can make the practice to work effectively, since their intervention role is dynamic that it can address almost all kind of social challenges.

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